

Reputation and Reach: Leveraging Branding to Elevate Non-Formal Education in the Digital Era

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Abstract

Background: Non-formal education is highly valued by the government and the community, particularly in the management of public education. The presence of this institution is needed in every social circle, not just in rural communities, but also in urban ones. Non-formal educational institutions are expected to carry out activities that can brand the institution, making it easier for the public to become familiar with the institution and its excellent programmes, so that people can make informed choices about meeting the community's needs for higher education that non-formal educational institutions provide.

Objective: This study aims to describe the branding of Package A's equality education learning services in promoting non-formal education through effective branding strategies.

Methodology: This research uses a qualitative research approach to gather in-depth data through interviews with key informants and observational fieldwork. The study employs a case study approach, focusing on the branding of equivalency education learning.

Results: This study demonstrates that learning equality education provides information and communication, enhances the image and attractiveness of these non-formal educational institutions in the community, makes the teaching and learning process unique and interesting, and enables the creation of a valuable learning experience for citizens.

Conclusion: Branding of equality education learning services to improve the image and attractiveness of non-formal educational institutions, answer the challenges of the digital era and strengthen competitive advantage.

Unique Contributions: The findings offer a distinct insight by showing that effective branding involves a multifaceted approach, specifically through improving the institutional image and attractiveness in the community, making the teaching and learning process unique and interesting, and creating a valuable learning experience for citizens.

Key recommendation: Branding studies can be conducted at other non-formal educational institutions to provide a space for comparison.

Keywords: Bridging, Non-formal education, branding, digital era

Introduction

Currently, it aligns with the development and needs of people from various circles. The presence of non-formal educational institutions aims to enhance the quality of institutional identity. How does non-formal education promote learning equality held by the community? Education serves as a pathway for individuals to develop in harmony with their inherent potential, and represents an academic institution in which community involvement replaces government involvement outside of conventional educational frameworks, to provide opportunities to individuals who have lost educational resources, thereby improving the overall quality of life in society (Mokh., 2021). Non-formal educational institutions represent educational entities designed for citizens who do not have the opportunity to engage or meet educational requirements at a certain level in the formal education system (Bafadhol, 2017; Ahmad, 2023). Meanwhile, according to Herwina et al. (2022), non-formal educational institutions serve individuals who have not yet engaged in or completed their education at a certain level within the framework of formal learning.

The community can manage non-formal education learning institutions as educational units or PKBM. One of the primary objectives of non-formal education is to facilitate equal learning, enabling individuals to obtain a recognised educational qualification alongside a formal education diploma. This educational program plays an important role in increasing access to education for marginalised groups and individuals who are unable to participate in formal education for various reasons (Rosmilawati, 2023). Several distinctive conclusions have emerged from the investigation conducted at PKBM Al Madinah, which underscores the importance of contextual community empowerment. Therefore, the role of PKBM Al Madinah in Kediri City is considered highly impactful in fostering an educational environment that encourages skill development in the community (Rochman et al., 2024). The structured nature of these programs ensures that learners acquire critical competencies that facilitate their reintegration into general education or the world of work.

Non-formal education is trying to overcome delays in the formal pathway. According to (Pienimaki et al. (2021), non-formal learning complements formal education and shares structural similarities with it. The Package A program's equality learning service is still in low demand; promotion to the community is needed through branding. Branding of learning services through educational programs at PKBM Al-Madinah. The institution's dedication to providing equal educational opportunities and resources to all students, regardless of background, should be communicated through branding that reflects educational equity (Celik, 2024). Branding educational services through programs at PKBM Al-Madinah is a vital process that aims to increase the perception and allure of educational institutions (Anang et al., 2020). The role of leadership in shaping brand perception is further demonstrated by the success of school leaders'

personal branding in Islamic boarding schools to foster trust between parents and potential students. The central aspect of branding in educational services centres on the quality of the academic and non-academic services provided. The quality of learning services is conceptualised as an effort to meet customer expectations and standards, improving academic and non-academic services that generate value and benefits (Rahmawati et al., 2023). The quality of educational services is a determining factor that significantly affects the student experience and the success of educational institutions in creating an effective learning environment. This quality covers various aspects ranging from teaching, facilities provided, to interaction between teachers and students. Prompt and pertinent academic services are necessary to facilitate a seamless educational process, thereby increasing students' loyalty to the school. Good service quality experiences can boost alumni and student brand engagement and help keep educational institutions viable (Hibatullah & Lindiawati, 2024).

Educational services, according to (Yang and Sigdel.,2023), emphasise the correlation between higher education services and institutional branding, highlighting the substantial impact that academic services have on student satisfaction, which, in turn, improves brand recognition and institutional reputation. the quality of e-learning services, including administrative support and advocacy materials, directly influences student satisfaction and loyalty, thereby strengthening educational institutions' brand equity. The dynamic components of substantial brand equity are important because they tend to increase consumer loyalty and often exceed consumer expectations for goods and services. The idea of customer-based brand equity, which prioritises the brand's perception and experience among consumers, is strongly tied to these strategies to build an image of communication among target groups with specific goals. Meanwhile, (Venessa and Arifin., 2017) define a brand as a symbol, sign, design, or combination thereof that can serve as an identity for various sellers or manufacturers, distinguishing them from competitors in the market. These three things can serve as the identity of several sellers or producers, later used as a differentiator from competitors in the market.

The importance of branding learning in non-formal education provides an opportunity for the community to continue acquiring knowledge and skills in high demand, thereby improving the quality of life. This research can analyse the obstacles and successes of educational institutions in the community to identify opportunities for continued education. The purpose of this study is to describe the success of branding non-formal educational institutions in providing education services needed by the community. The novelty or uniqueness of this research lies in promoting non-formal education by branding equality education program services that impact society. The methods used can influence the community to receive equality education, based on experience and the quality of educational programs, in accordance with economic needs and values.

Methodology

This study employed a qualitative methodology. The ability to gather more detailed and nuanced data is the driving force behind qualitative research, which facilitates the achievement of study objectives . Qualitative research approaches yield comprehensive insights (Sugiyono & Susy, 2022). The value underlying apparent data is research, which is actual data specific to the data. As a result, qualitative research places greater emphasis on meaning than on generalisations. With an emphasis on current phenomena, asserts that the case study research technique is a suitable

approach for inquiries that address the "how" and "why" concerns, particularly in situations where there is limited ability to organise the events being studied over time. Case studies can be successfully utilised for descriptive or explanatory purposes when the research is carefully planned and follows established protocols (Rustendi, 2023).

This study will explain equality education, learning, and branding. A case study is a comprehensive analysis of individuals, events, and backgrounds (including groups, organisations, or people). This study aims to gain a comprehensive understanding of a case under investigation—scholars who study meaningful programs, events, processes, or activities. The researcher employs a purposive sampling strategy, selecting informants who are considered knowledgeable about the issue under investigation. Five informants were interviewed by researchers, who asked them questions related to the pre-made guidelines framework. Direct communication with research participants is necessary to understand the background and implications of the data gathered. The researcher interviews each informant for 120 minutes until they have all the information they need, and can respond to the research question that the researcher has chosen. Since the researcher's role in this study is limited to observation, his presence falls under the category of passive participation in order to fully understand what is being witnessed. The following procedures are used to put observation into practice: (2) The researcher is present to gather information about the potential informant to be interviewed; (3) the researcher is present to search for documents deemed necessary as additional data; and (4) the researcher begins activities prior to entering the field by conducting pre-field service at PKBM, the location for the implementation of the A Branding learning equality education package, to obtain an overview.

Results and Discussion

Results

Based on the focus of the problem, the branding of the learning services of the equality programme package A includes: (1) the implementation of the package A equality program process at PKBM Al-Madinah, (2) the elements of the learning service of PKBM Al-Madinah, and (3) the function of the education unit's services for the community.

1. Branding of Learning Services for Package A Equality Program at PKBM Al-Madinah, Kediri City.

The branding of learning services for the A equality program at PKBM Al-Madinah Kediri City focuses on improving the image and attractiveness of this non-formal educational institution in the community. The opinion of informant Imadhul Bilad, as a community leader, explained the process of the equality program as follows:

Yes, Sir, it is strong, especially in the care system, which is carried out through visits to those in need and a network of agencies. PKBM Al-Madinah has great respect for public education, especially for those who do not attend school or drop out of school. The branding of package A services at PKBM Al-Madinah is very satisfying because this program is also aimed at residents who do not have the opportunity to get a formal education. Because in carrying out inclusive education, PKBM Al-Madinah must innovate and be creative with the branding of teaching program services. (IMA. F.SF.1)

Furthermore, informant Syailendra Yuda Crisilla also said, during the interview, that "branding equality learning services is a good promotion". This is interesting because it

involves the community in the learning process. Also conveyed by informant Nurul Handayani regarding the branding of the A equality learning package, as follows:

I think, Sir, it's good and very good because it has improved online and offline. This is very good because PKBM Al-Madinah has provided word-of-mouth information, brochures and social media regarding the quality of teaching, curriculum and educational procedures. Optimising PKBM Al-Madinah's TV media, social media, brochures/leaflets, parent communication WAGs, and offline forums for meetings with parents and community leaders. Consistent and creative service branding makes PKBM Al-Madinah increasingly known to many people. The branding of the service carried out is by digitising learning activities and extra activities, participating in competitions from the Regional level to the National level, so that many achievements are achieved by the children of PKBM Al-Madinah Package A. (NUR. F.SF.1)

Strategic and integrated use of various existing communication media to attract public interest in their educational programs. Putri Rahayu said that "with social media, consistent and creative service branding makes PKBM Al-Madinah more known to many people". Furthermore, informant Imadhul Bilad provided information, "The branding of the service carried out is by digitising learning activities and extra activities, participating in competitions from the regional level to the national level, so that many achievements are achieved by the children of package A PKBM Al.-Madinah". This shows that educational units can carry out branding learning to enhance the quality of the Al-Madinah PKBM institution. The researcher then collected data by gathering documents in the form of pictures and data on students participating in the learning services of the package A program, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Equality Education Learning Process

Based on the results of field findings, it can be concluded that the learning services of the equality education program package A are as follows: (1) branding of educational learning services provides a satisfactory image for students and the community, (2) learning services provide opportunities for the community to be able to learn for those who drop out of school, (3) provide digitalized learning information that students and the community can access.

2. Elements of PKBM Al-Madinah Learning Services

The elements of the learning service in the A package A equality program at PKBM Al-Madinah, Kediri City, in learning branding encompass all aspects that make the teaching and

learning process unique and interesting. According to information from Syailendra Yuda Crisilla, these elements were built as a promotion of educational units, as follows:

This is good, sir. The implementation of the curriculum and a personal approach with various stakeholders is good. Digital promotion and community-based collaboration can be further improved. The elements of learning services in Package A of PKBM Al-Madinah are very good, starting from a curriculum that suits their needs, tutors who have the ability and experience in teaching, comfortable and adequate facilities for the learning process and the latest and effective technology to improve the quality of learning. This is very good so that learning can also run well, and with the hope of all parents/guardians of students and partners in it. (SYA. F.SF.2)

Furthermore, when interviewed, informant Putri Rahayu explained that the emphasis on effective, quality, and citizen learning highlights a citizen-centred approach and prioritises active participation in the teaching and learning process. This learning is carried out as follows:

The branding of learning at PKBM Al-Madinah is very interesting because it adjusts to the child's talents and interests. Innovative learning can be one of the advantages of education in an institution, and in an exciting extracurricular program, it can be an attraction in itself. This extracurricular program not only provides students with the opportunity to develop their special interests and talents but also builds additional skills and character necessary for life outside the classroom. (PUT. F.SF.2)

PKBM Al-Madinah not only provides education in general, but also tries to recognise and accommodate the uniqueness of each student in terms of their talents and interests. This was explained by informant Imadhul Bilad when interviewed as follows:

In my opinion, Sir, be proactive in carrying out marketing strategies that are in accordance with the needs of PKBM Al Medina. This approach involves an in-depth analysis of educational trends, community preferences, and factors influencing the decision of parents or prospective students who want to study at PKBM Al Madinah. Improving Service Branding does indeed need to always maintain and even increase commitment to what has been implemented for it is necessary: 1. there is evaluation and follow-up for improvement, 2. as long as efforts are made to improve the competence of existing human resources as an effort to improve the quality of services provided, 3. oriented to the interests or needs (learned citizens) of the community in providing services. 4. Conducting publications and activities that are known to the wider community. (IMA. F.SF.2)

By continuing to pay attention to and develop the importance of branding, strategic marketing, and a commitment to continuous service quality improvement, PKBM Al-Madinah has great potential to continue moving forward and make a significant contribution to the world of equality education. The researcher then collected data in the form of images and student data using Figure 2.

Figure 2. Elements of Learning Services

Based on the results of the field findings, it can be concluded that the elements of the equality education learning service package A are as follows: (1) having comfortable and adequate facilities for the learning process as well as the latest technology to improve the quality of learning effectively, (2) extracurricular programs provide students with the opportunity to develop talent interests that build additional skills and character necessary for life outside class.

3. Role and Function of Institutional Services to Parents or the Community

The Package A equality program at PKBM Al-Madinah Kediri City plays an important role in improving access to education for the community, especially for parents or people who have children who have dropped out of school or have never attended school. It is said that the informant, Syailendra Yuda Crisilla, related to the service functions provided by the community as follows:

This institution is very helpful for the interests of the community, both in the academic and vocational fields. It is very helpful for the community in the field of education, a practical solution for parents in choosing a school/place for their children to learn according to their child's potential and needs. The Al-Madinah Foundation is very concerned about the community, especially for children who drop out of school, so that they can continue their education. It is also very helpful for children who are already working or want to focus on memorising the Quran, but still want to get a formal school diploma. (SYA. F.SF.3)

Furthermore, informant Putri Rahayu explained that the provision of services and institutions that are satisfactory in providing good social welfare is carried out as a function and role given. Then it was emphasised that the informant stated as follows:

In my opinion, Sir Baik, the institution has provided services to the surrounding community well, and also established a good relationship with the parents of

students. The role and function of institutional services are very influential in improving the quality of education and community welfare, so that they can strengthen the relationship between institutions, parents, and the community. Its function is as a bridge of knowledge, service, and solutions to various problems in an educational institution between tutors and the community. (PUT. F.SF.3)

Strengthening excellent programs, improving the quality of educational services, and actively communicating with the community form part of continuous efforts to enhance the quality of educational services, increase the competitiveness of institutions, and provide added value for residents and the learning community. Informant Moh. Nizar Nasrodin Salim, when interviewed, said the following:

Yes, sir. The role and function of institutional services to parents are: 1) Providing education and training to parents or the community on various relevant topics. 2) Providing guidance and counselling to parents or people in need. 3) Increase awareness and knowledge of parents or the community on various relevant topics. Most parents have a positive perception of the service institution at PKBM Al-Madinah. Their knowledge of PNF was built because of intense socialisation by the PKBM Al-Medina institution. They assessed that PNF provides learning flexibility for their children to gain more knowledge, along with hands-on experience in the field. (MOH. F.SF.3)

The involvement of the community and parents is an important component in the school's efforts to improve the quality of school services, for example, enhancing the competence of all school elements, including tutors and principals. The researcher then collected data by gathering documents, including drawings and student records, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Roles and Functions of Parents or Society

Based on the results of the field findings, it can be concluded that the Role and Function of Parents or the Community is to increase access to education, enabling the community to play an active role in culture, as well as supporting parents who have children who have dropped out of school or never attended school.

Discussion

Branding of learning services for the equality education program at PKBM Al-Madinah Kediri City, which is an effort to achieve success. The results of research findings in the field show that

the Branding implementation program has several components, as follows: (1) branding education learning services provide a satisfactory image for the community to be able to learn for school dropouts digitally accessible to students and the community; (2) have convenient and adequate facilities for the learning process as well as the latest technology to effectively improve the quality of learning, develop talent interests that build additional skills and character necessary for life outside the classroom; (3) Improving access to education for the community, especially for parents or people who have children who have dropped out of school or have never attended school. Branding in education encompasses a wide range of frameworks and best practices, reflecting the unique challenges and opportunities educators face while incorporating broader branding principles from the commercial realm. Educational institutions, faced with increasingly stiff competition and an ever-evolving demographic, are increasingly recognising the importance of building a strong brand identity that aligns with prospective students, parents, and society..

These results are consistent with the notion of brand awareness. Research indicates that learners' admissions decisions are significantly impacted by greater brand knowledge. To effectively lead students through the admissions process and influence public image, a robust brand strategy is necessary (Duc & Vu, 2024). This demonstrates that building a comprehensive image aligned with the goals and values of the target audience is just as important to branding as increasing visibility. Furthermore, the brand ecosystem framework offers a comprehensive approach to creating a branding plan tailored to educational institutions. According to this paradigm, successful branding goes beyond simple marketing strategies and is based on students' interactions and experiences with businesses. Institutions can develop captivating stories that foster a stronger emotional bond with their constituents by focusing on the entire educational journey.

These results highlight the importance of aligning marketing messaging with potential students' identity ambitions. The results of the study show that the definition of branding in education provides a good image for student acceptance through good explanations. Branding is crucial in education because it can significantly shape perceptions among students, parents, and the broader community. This opinion concludes that branding in education involves a multifaceted approach that includes brand awareness, emotional engagement, cultural equity, and strategic management. Educational institutions must develop a strong, coherent brand identity that resonates emotionally with their audiences, thereby fostering loyalty and improving recruitment and retention. All things considered, a holistic approach involving reputation management, digital innovation, internal cohesiveness, and community engagement is necessary for an educational institution to market itself effectively. Institutions must understand that their brand identity not only represents their educational programs but also increasingly defines their standing and sustainability in the global education market as the educational landscape grows more competitive (Xia, 2024).

Effective branding plays a crucial role in fostering and maintaining a positive image, and effective communication is integral to developing educational brands, emphasising the need for clear, consistent, and relevant messaging to build a strong educational brand. Trainees have a big impact on training results, according to (Abdurochman et al., 2024). Therefore, PKBM must effectively convey the benefits of Package A through various platforms. Furthermore, it is impossible to overlook the revolutionary significance that digital platforms play in modern branding initiatives. To ensure that perceived messages align with institutional principles and reinforce corporate

identity, digital communication strategies must be integrated (Thang & Phong, 2022). An educational institution's standing can be significantly enhanced by a well-executed digital branding plan, thereby increasing its awareness and reputation. Brand image and increased brand awareness are positively connected, indicating that organisations with a strong brand presence are better able to provide stakeholders with high-quality education (Marhareita et al., 2022). With the rise of social media, institutions have unprecedented opportunities to raise awareness and communicate their commitment to educational excellence. Additionally, a supportive and inclusive learning environment, along with adequate learning facilities and resources, significantly impacts student motivation and educational outcomes. Branding should portray a warm, inclusive, and motivating learning atmosphere.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the research and the discussion of the results, in general, it can be concluded that (1) The branding of equality education learning package A at PKBM Al-Madinah has a program aimed at residents who do not have the opportunity to receive formal education in implementing inclusive education; (2) consistent and creative services make PKBM Al-Madinah increasingly known by many people by digitizing learning activities, extra activities supported by learning infrastructure facilities; (3) The emphasis on practical, qualitative, and citizen-engaged learning highlights a citizen-centered approach and prioritizes active participation in the teaching and learning process. This is evidenced by the community's involvement, including participation in learning equality education each year. Equality education learning also competes with formal education in terms of quality, both in terms of knowledge and skills.

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